

First report on Impact Analysis

D2.8

If we are providing the right communication means and products to the right people through the right channel at the right moment then it is quite likely that we are having an impact in terms of communication¹

Document information Summary

Date	15 September 2017
Document title	First report on Impact Analysis
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Approved by	Implementation Phase Council
Target audiences	Project partners, EC
Keywords	Dissemination, Communication, Impact
Deliverable nature	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Delivery date	M24 Key Deliverable
Version n/date	9/15 September 2017

¹The basic rules in the evaluation of communication activities - Third meeting of INFORM Community network of Regional Policy communication officers 15-16 June 2009 – DG Communication Enrique Garcia Martin-Romo http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/archive/country/commu/docevent/15062009/EnriqueGarciaMartinRomo.ppt

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the first report on the impact of the EPOS communication activities.

Communication is a vector to achieve the full exploitation of results which is a precondition for guaranteeing scientific and socio-economic impact. Indeed, only when potential stakeholders become aware of EPOS and of what EPOS can do for them, its products and services can be exploited. In turn, only if products and services are fully exploited, we can affirm an impact on science and/or on society is achieved. Accordingly, to secure the project would achieve a satisfactory scientific and socio-economic impact, we must first ensure we are having an impact in terms of communication. However, the impact of communication activities can be very difficult to measure because there can be a significant delay before any apparent effect. Nevertheless, by constantly evaluating and monitoring our communication activities, so that communication tools are continuously modulated and tailored accordingly, we make sure that the Communication Plan is effectively applied. This will, in turn, ensure communication has an impact and its assessment can be done in a more concrete framework.

The role of WP2 is to ensure that the EPOS Communication Plan is effectively applied; Task 2.6, in particular, is in charge of gathering both qualitative and quantitative data (statistics), and of defining metrics to measure and monitor the impact of EPOS IP's communication, including outreach, dissemination and training activities.

This document briefly: (i) recalls the objectives of the communication activities as identified at the beginning of the project and reported in the Communication Plan (Chapter 2); (ii) describes the methodology and processes used to monitor the communication activities as identified before EPOS began and throughout the life of the project (Chapter 3); (iii) reports on the results of the monitoring performed up to M23 (Chapter 4), giving a preliminary analysis of the impact.

In the subsequent deliverable (M48 D2.9) we will report on our analysis of the monitoring and on the elaboration of the results to assess the impact of EPOS communication at the end of the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

The EPOS Implementation Phase (IP) project is an enormous endeavour involving 25 countries, 138 institutions, 250 National Research Infrastructures, thousands of observing stations and hundreds of instruments producing several petabyte of data available for several thousands of users including, but not limited, to scientists. EPOS will enable cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary research and promote the development of new research concepts and tools. EPOS will provide accurate, lasting and sustainable answers to societal questions by empowering researchers to better understand how planet Earth works as a system and thus address geo-hazards and geo-resources challenges. This, in turn, will help funding agencies and decision-makers to better address safeguarding of the environment and the welfare of society.

The role of communication

Communication plays an important role for enabling EPOS to reach its objectives. For the overall success of the EPOS Infrastructure, effective communication must be ensured at two levels: internal and external. Internal communication within the EPOS IP consortium will ensure effective project collaboration between the thematic communities as they develop their services and provide their data and across the IT team as they design and develop the needed infrastructure for developing the EPOS integrated delivery framework. Internal communication also includes bridging between the diverse competences covered by the different groups of experts collaborating in EPOS IP. The successful development of the EPOS delivery framework requires several teams of experts in very different areas of expertise to cooperate and “speak the same language”. A huge communication effort was required right from the start of the project, for the elicitation of requirements from different communities (from the Earth Science but also from the policy and legal environment), and translation of domain specific requirements into technical requirements for the IT team to develop an integrated framework capable of offering the needed services and satisfying a heterogeneous set of requirements. Data policy, for instance, is an important aspect which entails concepts of privacy and security as well as intellectual property. The policies to be adopted to share data in the EPOS framework are being carefully studied by the TCS community jointly with WP6 and WP7 (in charge of coordinating the activity for data sharing) and WP4 (in charge of coordinating the activities for data policy). Effective internal communication is needed to define the requirements and specifications for successful development of the EPOS framework. However, potential stakeholders (e.g. scientists, governments, society) can fully exploit the EPOS products and services only if they become aware of EPOS and what it can do for them. External communication is needed to reach external stakeholders such as scientists in or outside the solid Earth science domain, governments, the private sector and society.

Scope of the document

The Communication Work Package (WP2), led by INGV, is responsible for managing the communication and dissemination activities as described in the EPOS IP Communication Plan. Ensuring effective communication, however, it is only the first step: it is necessary to evaluate and monitor the communication activities in place so that their effectiveness can be assessed and the adopted tools tuned accordingly. To this end, WP2 is also in charge of evaluating the success of the communication activities in order to manage, improve and maximise their impact throughout the project’s life. In particular, Task 2.6 in WP2 is responsible for gathering both qualitative and quantitative data (statistics) and for defining the metrics to measure and monitor the impact of EPOS IP’s communication, including outreach, dissemination and training activities. Task 2.6 is focused on monitoring and measuring the impact of the communication activities in the EPOS IP project.

Measuring impact is notoriously difficult as it can be far-reaching and complex, and may not become fully apparent until years later. The impact of communication activities, in particular, can be even more difficult to measure because it is short-lived and there is often a significant delay before any apparent effect. Nevertheless, increasing emphasis is being placed on this measurement leading to new methods and processes being constantly developed and utilised.

WP2's strategy for assessing communication impact in EPOS has been to first define realistic objectives for communication activities and the impacts we are expecting to observe and then to identify the most efficient methods to monitor the activities. Reporting on this is the aim of the present document. Finally, it is worth noting that WP2 works closely with the Impact Monitoring and Assessment Group established in WP3 to assess the impact concerning the scientific and socio-economic value of EPOS. This synergy is necessary for the final evaluation of the effectiveness of the communication strategy that has been adopted.

2. THE EPOS VISION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

EPOS aims to create a pan-European infrastructure to enable scientific research on solid Earth processes supporting a safe and sustainable society. In accordance with this scientific vision, the EPOS mission is to integrate the diverse and advanced European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth science to monitor and unravel the dynamic and complex Earth system while taking advantages of new e-science opportunities.

Through integration of data, models and facilities EPOS will allow the Earth Science community to make a step change in developing new concepts and tools for answering key scientific and socio-economic questions concerning geo-hazards and geo-resources as well as Earth science applications to the environment and to human welfare. At the very beginning of the project life EPOS outlined the following main objectives in the Communication Plan (D2.1 M6):

- *engage effectively with stakeholders*, to help achieving this objective, the stakeholders' classification defined during the Preparatory Phase has been slightly revised to disaggregate categories into target audiences (see Table 1); this allows us to focus communication on tightly defined audiences within the broad EPOS stakeholder categories;
- *ensure people understand what EPOS does*, implying to keep the already engaged partners interested and involved as well as attracting further potential partners;
- *change behaviour and perceptions* where necessary, this can be achieved by enhancing the reputation and visibility of EPOS at local, national, and international level and by creating the transfer of knowledge among heterogeneous communities;
- *help achieve the overall EPOS objectives* or, in other words, promote the full exploitation of results, which is the overarching goal of communication.

These objectives have been the basis for defining the Communication strategy that was implemented during the first 24 months of the project.

Table 1. Stakeholder's categories and target audiences in EPOS IP

Stakeholders' category	Target audience
Scientists	Data Providers
	Data users within the solid earth community
	Data users outside the solid earth community
	IT experts
Governments	National governments
	Funding agencies
	European commission
Private sector	Industry
	Small and Medium Enterprises (SME)
Society	Students at any level
	General public

3. METHODOLOGY AND PROCESS

What is "impact"?

First of all, it is beneficial to briefly define what is meant by "impact": there are several different levels at which impact can be considered, often referred to as the "Three O's".

The first level of impact is the project's **outputs**: an example of an output is the participation in conferences, the publication of scientific papers or the production of dissemination material. Outputs are objective and quantifiable, so careful management of the project can keep precise track of them. The measure of outputs gives information on the amount of work that is being performed and its first level results. The value of outputs, however, goes beyond their simple number. Participation in a conference, for instance, can be more or less valuable depending on the audience and the kind of engagement achieved. Going one step further, it is possible to analyse the **outgrowth**, e.g. how many people attended the EPOS session at a conference? Measuring the outgrowth of activities provides a deeper level of insight into the relevance of the results achieved. Finally, for a deeper understanding it is important to analyse the **outcome** of project's activities, which is the actual long-term or indirect effects: e.g. Earth scientists using integrated EPOS platform services to correlate data from different disciplines to generate reliable predictions of geological hazard events.

Impact measurement and KPIs

In order to understand the actual return on it's investment, the EC requires funded projects to provide objective documentation of the impact achieved from their activities and effort spent. This is becoming more and more important as the EC is increasingly concerned with the way contributors' money is spent, and transparency is highly valued. *"It is not possible to manage what you cannot control and you cannot control what you cannot measure!"* (Peter Drucker). Defining performance indicators (Table 2) upfront is now required to keep project activities running in the right direction. Regular monitoring of performance indicators allows wise project management that highlights the gaps between desired and measured results and provides timely indication of how to close them. Continuous monitoring enables the project's strategy to be adjusted to changing needs and to put in place corrective actions in a timely fashion if the trend is not

as desired. Defining suitable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (Table 2) is the first step in setting up a monitoring procedure that leads towards a project achieving its desired impacts. KPIs identify a set of representative indicators that can be used to provide a reasonable/tangible measurement of the success of a project. Good KPIs should be SMART: that is, Specific to the objective, Measurable, Achievable in a cost-effective way, Relevant for the programme and Time bound so that is clear when it is to be achieved.

The EPOS Communication Plan identifies a set of communication activities to be performed from the start of the project. The communication activities defined in D2.1 are based on the target audience as shown in Table 1. The output of each activity has been identified together with possible key performance indicators (KPIs). (See preliminary version of KPIs in Communication Plan D2.1 at M6, and a consolidated version at M24). Expected impact and KPIs (to be used to gauge performance in terms of meeting strategic and operational goals) have been identified since the beginning of the project to allow for a solid and coherent monitoring of the activities to generate continuous and systematic data. This monitoring is necessary to help identify and address any possible problems affecting the performance of the activities at the same time as it generates data for evaluation and impact assessment. However, expected impact and KPIs reported in the M6 version of the Communication Plan were necessarily very general whereas in this document a more detailed overview of the parameters used to monitor and measure effectiveness of the communication activities and the results of monitoring is provided. The data used for the monitoring is mostly based on information provided in deliverables, periodic reports and/or obtained via statistical analysis of various media.

These consolidated KPIs are mainly related to project outputs which are clearly measurable: they provide an objective, **quantitative** way of assessing the progress of project activities at any point in time and to measure the distance from expected results. The list of EPOS' KPIs adopted to assess communication impact is displayed in table 2 (column 1). For each KPI the table indicates the expected outputs by month 24 (30 September 2017), the actual achievement at month 23 (31 August 2017) and an evaluation of the progress status represented by the ratio between the achieved and expected outputs (column 3). The fourth column represents the preliminary impact analysis made at M24. The impact assessment reported in this document through the analysis depicted in Table 2 should be considered a retrospective evaluation since the expected achievements have been identified during the assessment at M23. The M48 assessment will be undertaken with the expected achievements identified at M25, and possibly revised at M36.

It should be noted that significant amounts of data for assessing impact will only become available in the later stages of the project. As previously recognised, there are both qualitative and quantitative approaches to evaluating impact. A combination of both, which is referred to as 'Mixed Method', was adopted. **Quantitative** evaluation (i.e. KPI monitoring) answers the 'how much' or 'how many' questions and provides numbers and statistics. Whereas **qualitative** methods are good for evaluation of questions that ask 'what', 'how' or 'why'; these methods are particularly useful for providing a deep understanding of socio-economic impacts which are hard to measure in clear and simple quantitative terms, but are also among the most important types of impact. Qualitative evaluations include, for example, interviews with stakeholders, feedback questionnaires and quotes that can be collected during workshops or events. Both quantitative and qualitative measurements provide input data to be analysed in detail for deriving improvements in the communication activities.

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators, monitoring results, and analysis of communication impact at M23

KPI Category	KPI	Expected outputs	Achieved outputs	Impact assessment	Impact Analysis*
Events organised by EPOS	Scientific events	15	66	440%	High
	Governmental events	2	12	600%	High
	Private sector events	4	3	75%	Low
Events EPOS participated to	Scientific events	30	115	383%	High
	Governmental events	4	3	75%	Low
	Private sector events	1	1	100%	expected
Participation to projects/initiatives	Scientific projects/initiatives within SES	2	2	100%	expected
	IT projects/initiatives	2	2	100%	expected
	Other projects/initiatives	2	2	100%	expected
Outreach	Articles	2	26	130%	High
	Position Papers	1	1	100%	expected
	Press Releases	2	2	100%	expected
	Interviews	10	13	130%	High
	Brochures / Flyers / etc	20	20	100%	expected
	Posters	20	36	180%	High
	Videos	1	2	200%	High
Website	Unique visitors (weekly avg.)	300	440	146%	High
Social Media	Twitter				
	Tweets (weekly avg.)	5	12	240%	High
	Followers	300	620	206%	High
	LinkedIn				
	Posts/Updates	20	16	80%	Low
	Community	200	2130	106%	High
	Facebook				
	Contacts	124	290	233%	High
	Likes	124	291	234%	High
	YouTube				
Channel Subscribers	19	32	168%	High	
Likes	14	18	128%	High	
Flickr					
Views	20000	21700	108%	High	
Newsletter	Subscribers	800	1106	138%	High
	Readers	300	380	126%	High
Training	Training initiative	15	16	106%	High
	Trainees	300	705	235%	High
	People involved in training	12	35	291%	High
Intranet	Intranet members	300	640	210%	High
	Sessions	---	16000	---	

*: High>100%; expected =100%; Low<100%

4. MONITORING RESULTS

This chapter provides detailed monitoring results for the communication tools e.g. website, social media etc. for the period from the beginning of the EPOS-IP project (1st October 2015) until M23 (31 August 2017). Further details on the other communication activities, can be found in deliverable D2.4 (where, among other dissemination and communication activities, events are described) and D2.6 (training).

Website

During the period from 1st October 2015 to 31 August 2017 (M23) the EPOS website registered over 43,000 sessions (*Figure 1*) and 26,353 visitors. During each session an average of 3 pages were visited. Over 40% of visitors landed on the EPOS pages from an organic search, while 32% came from an external link and 21% directly accessed the EPOS website. A total of 5.6% of visits to the EPOS website came from social media channels, this number has grown to 6.7% during the second year of the project, reflecting the increased resources being spent in social media engagement activities. The most popular page visited was the 'About EPOS' page with 4,425 page visualisations. The second and third most popular pages were the 'News' and 'Our Partners' pages with 1,891 and 1,882 page views respectively, followed by the 'Events' page with 1,880 visits. During the second year of the project both the number of sessions and visitors has increased. Regular weekly monitoring of these numbers is showing constant growth, with peaks corresponding to release of the Newsletters and to project and community events.

Figure 1. Monthly website sessions M1-M23

Social media

Social media has been shown to be a very useful complementary dissemination channel for promoting EPOS and, in particular, events, publications and newsletters. The power of social media must be harnessed by EPOS as a means of reaching out to a wider and more diverse audience. However, due to the nature of the EPOS IP project, and to the current development phase, communication to date has mainly focused on the project partners, solid earth scientists and IT professionals. The EPOS project is utilising a wide variety of social media including Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Slideshare (not yet operational), Flickr and YouTube. Activity across all of these social media platforms has constantly increased in the reporting period (M1-M23).

Figure 2. A sample of EPOS tweets

Twitter

Twitter is a key communication tool for informal community building both within the EPOS consortium and also with the wider user community. It is used to build collaborative links with other projects, strengthen interactions among project partners and communicate with scientists and researchers. The EPOS Twitter channel, @EPOSeu, is used both to broadcast the latest project news and for live tweeting during EPOS events e.g. during the EPOS session at the European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly 2016. Content-rich, targeted and timely tweets promote the development of the EPOS social media community: the number of Twitter followers has been steadily growing reaching over 600 in August 2017. Tweets are reaching an increasing audience, with impressions growing constantly from 2,100 impressions during the first quarter of the projects (Oct/Dec 2015), up to 165,000 impressions during the second quarter of 2017, which is also due in part to the multiplier effect of high-profile Twitter users following EPOS. The level of engagement (i.e. the percentage of tweets that triggered a reaction such as a click, a like or a retweet) has been growing, from an initial 0.5% in the first quarter of the project (Oct/Dec 2015) up to 0.9% in the second quarter of 2017. On average EPOS Tweets reached over 6,000 people every week over the reporting period (M1-M23). The number of tweets has increased reaching a stable average of around three tweets per working day. During the period from M1 to M23 EPOS Tweets reached 644,500 impressions, receiving over 3,800 interactions (1,748 link clicks, 957 retweets and 1,119 likes). On average, EPOS Tweets reached around 1,000 people each day with the top three Tweets leading to 194 interactions. Figure 2 illustrates some of the most popular tweets, highlighting the heterogeneous audience that is addressed: ranging from solid earth

scientists to IT specialists and covering both partners and external audience. Tweets about recent earthquakes gained high levels of interactions reflecting the interest that can be created when reacting to topical events and linking how EPOS can contribute to such situations.

Many research institutions in the Earth Science domain follow the EPOS Twitter account including a number of highly prestigious organisations engaged in Solid Earth Science (Table 3).

Table 3. Research institution following EPOS Twitter

Category	Name	Handle	Description
University departments	UiB Earth Science:	@uibgeo	Department of Earth Science of the University of Bergen
	GIIS	@GIIS_UPM	Earthquake Engineering Research Group, Technical University Madrid
Geological associations	BGSseismology	@BGSseismology	British Geological Survey's Seismology team
	MineralogicalSociety	@MinSoc_UK	The Mineralogical Society of Great Britain and Ireland is an international society for all those working in the mineral sciences.
	Geological Survey of Norway	@nguweb	Norges Geologiske Undersøkelse / Geological Survey of Norway.
	Geological Survey Belgium	@GSBelgium	The Geological Survey of Belgium (GSB) is a research unit of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
	Geological Survey Ireland	@GeolSurvIE	Geological Survey Ireland
Clusters of research organisations	EarthCube	@EarthCube	A community-led @NSF program that advances partnerships, collaborative platforms across the #geosciences.
	ENEON	@ENEONetwork	European Network of Earth Observation Networks, funded by EU under H2020
	EFG	@EfgInfo	The EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF GEOLOGISTS, EFG, is the Voice of European Geologists. NGO established in 1980, including today 25 national association members.
	EGU GMPV Division	@EGU_GMPV	Geochemistry, Mineralogy, Petrology, Volcanology Division (GMPV) of the European Geosciences Union (EGU)
	CASRAI	@casrai	A global non-profit consortia of research institutions agreeing on non-technical information standards to reduce paperwork & improve quality.
Crisis management organisations	HUKM	@cro_crisis_mgmt	Croatian Crisis Management Association (HUKM) - Association for Promotion and Development of Crisis and Disaster Management
	VOST ANDALUCIA	@VOSTandalucia	Equipo de voluntarios digitales en emergencias
	IAPG-Nigeria	@iapg_nigeria	Official twitter handle of the International Association for Promoting Geoethics Nigeria section-IAPG Nigeria IUGS, AGI, GSA, GSL, GIRAF and NMGS affiliated

The number of followers from communities such as computer science, IT, data science and networking reflects the level of interest in the development of new and innovative approaches by EPOS (Table 4).

Table 4. Projects related to e-Infrastructure and Open Data in Europe

Follower	Handle	Multiplier effect (followers)
ENVRIplus	@ENVRIplus	500+
EUDAT	@Eudat_EU	2,300+
RDA	@resdatall	6,100+
GÉANT	@GEANTNews	2,500+
CORDIS	@CORDIS_EU	18,000+
EinfraEU	@eInfraEu	2,700+
Horizon 2020	@EU_H2020	65,000+
EU open Data	@EU_opendata	12,900
OpenAire	@OpenAIRE_eu	7,300+

EPOS also uses social media including Twitter to engage with Industry, students and the general public. Some of the Twitter followers in these groups include:

- Educational organisations targeted for young generations of students such as
 - EarthLearningIdea (@ELI_Earth)
 - CESAR (@esa_cesar_en)
 - Geocorsi -elearning platform (@geocorsi)
- Organisations that are specialised in disseminating scientific results to the general public
 - Volunteer Science (@VolunteerSci)
 - SciTech - sharing amazing science and technology tweets (@scitechshares)
 - Geoscience Frontiers - a unique free to publish Open Access journal hosted by Elsevier, covering all fields of Geoscience (@GeosciFrontiers)
- Industry
 - Mepeco S.r.l. - technology for Oil, Gas, Geothermal projects and Marine and Coastal Sciences. (@Mepecoagent)

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account for EPOS was set up at the beginning of October 2016. During the period from 1st October 2016 to 31st August 2017 19 articles and updates were posted. Building of the LinkedIn EPOS community was initiated by first inviting all the EPOS IP project partners and then extending invitations to other relevant researchers and industry stakeholders. By the 31st August 2017, the EPOS LinkedIn community has reached over 2,000 followers from across Europe, principally geologists, Earth science researchers and graduate assistants, university professors and lecturers, but also individuals employed in the mechanical industry and in the Oil and Energy sector, mining and metals and environmental services. This reflects the heterogeneous community of stakeholders in the complex solid earth science domain.

Facebook

The EPOS Facebook page, available at the following link <https://www.facebook.com/EPOS-European-Plate-Observing-System-155473037830465/> was given a lower priority in the first two years of the project. Facebook is a more informal communication channel which is mainly updated with automatic procedures that repost news from the EPOS website, tweets and images from other social media channels: news items and tweets from the newsletters, news and events published in the EPOS website, tweets on Twitter, images on Flickr and video on YouTube channel). Some of the key Facebook metrics monitored are:

- The total number of people who have liked EPOS Page (Unique Users)
- The number of Unlikes of EPOS Page (Unique Users)
- The number of people who have engaged with EPOS Page. Engagement includes any click or story created (Unique Users)
- The number of people who saw the EPOS Page or one of its posts from a story shared by a friend. These stories include liking a Page, posting to a Page's timeline, liking, etc.
- The number of impressions seen of any content associated with a Page (Total Count)

From the beginning of the EPOS IP project, the total number of followers and likes has increased constantly: on October 2015, the page counted 124 followers, at M24 they are 290. The total number of people who liked the Page (Unique Users) increased from 124 up to 291. Figure 3 shows the number of people who have seen any content associated with EPOS page. The graphic divides users by age and gender, grouping them also per Countries and language.

Country	People Reach...	City	People Reach...	Language	People Reach...
Italy	64	Rome, Lazio, Italy	24	English (US)	94
United States of America	44	Reykjavík, Capital Regi...	23	Italian	60
Iceland	35	Athens, Attica (region),...	13	English (UK)	34
Greece	33	Mexico City, Distrito Fe...	12	Greek	25
France	21	Bergen, Hordaland, No...	5	French (France)	18
Mexico	17	Kraków, Lesser Poland...	5	Spanish	16
Poland	15	Bucharest, Romania	5	Polish	15
Norway	11	Hafnarfjörður, Capital ...	4	Icelandic	13

Figure 3. People who have seen any content associated with EPOS page

YouTube

The EPOS YouTube channel is available at the following link:
<https://www.youtube.com/user/eposeu?feature=hovercard>

During the first 12 months of the project, three videos have been updated on the channel:

- EPOS Seismology- An Interview with Florian Haslinger - 26 views
- The -importance of EPOS- an interview with Kuvvet Atakan - 26 views
- EPOS Volcano Observations - an interview with Kristin Vogfjord - 18 views

The videos with the most views during the first year are those published during the preparatory phase which describe the Community Services (905 views); the EPOS USE CASES - the future of integrated services (520 views); and the EPOS DEMONSTRATOR (96 views).

In the second year of the project the EPOS YouTube channel has been updated with ten playlists, corresponding to each EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS). A new EPOS video: *Viable solutions to tackle solid Earth grand challenges*, updated in July reached 2017 received 925 views in just a few months. Figure 4 compares the EPOS channel statistics for 2016 and 2017.

Figure 4. YouTube statistics 2016 and 2017

Flickr

The EPOS Flickr channel <https://www.flickr.com/people/eposeu/> was created in December 2011 during the Preparatory Phase. In the second year of the EPOS IP project the account has been updated with new galleries of images taken during EPOS events. There are three followers and there have been 21,000 views of this channel.

Newsletter

During the Preparatory Phase (PP) the preferences and interests of the EPOS Newsletter readers have been monitored to guide the planning for future editions. This led to a re-organisation of the contents, the graphic design and frequency of issues during the IP project. Compared to the Newsletters released during the PP, the IP Newsletter contains more sections and new contents focused on attracting the interest of new and old readers, and communicating the EPOS innovation and how it is adding value to existing national research infrastructures. The Newsletter, once ready to be disseminated, is distributed using the MailChimp tool, to a mailing list of subscribers to the EPOS website and the EPOS Intranet mailing list. This tool creates statistics measuring e.g. the number of subscribers, the number of people opening the Newsletters, and the unique clicks. It is also possible to obtain the number of top links clicked and the top locations by opens (Table 5). The number of subscribers to the EPOS newsletter increased from 551 (December 2014) to 1106 (September 2017) and, consequently, the average of the open rate and click rate (number of readers and of numbers of unique click on the contents) has also increased. The statistics for the EPOS website indicate a peak in traffic that closely correlates with the release dates of the Newsletters with many of the views and hits corresponding to the links and topics mentioned in the Newsletter.

Table 5. Overview of the Newsletter numbers at M24, M12 and during the PP

Overview M24	
Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1106	
Subscribers from EPOS intranet: 990; Subscribers from website: 116	
Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
38%	380
Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
11%	108
Overview M12	
Total number of Subscribed Contacts: 1029	
% Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
44%	389
% Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
16%	142
Overview Preparatory Phase	
Total number of subscribed contacts: 540	
% Average open rate	Average open rate - number of readers
40%	213
% Average click rate	Average click rate – number of readers
17%	89

Intranet

Due to the high number of partners, their geographical distribution and their constant need to coordinate and keep each other up to date, EPOS uses a collaborative area, the so called “Intranet” designed as an integrated instrument to facilitate internal communication among partners. At time of writing, the EPOS Intranet has over 640 active registered users. During the period from December 2015 to August 31st 2017 (M23) the EPOS Intranet website registered over 16,000 sessions, and over 3,000 visitors demonstrating that it responds to concrete community needs. During each session an average of 5 pages were visited.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The complex nature of the EPOS IP project and the scale of the implementation phase requires effective planning of communication activities and efficient monitoring of outputs, outgrowth and outcomes in order to undertake an impact assessment for these activities. In particular, high impact internal communication is essential to ensure awareness of the EPOS mission, share efforts to foster achievements, maintain workflow and timeline, share responsibilities for risk management. Fostering high impact of external communication is vital to guarantee full exploitation of results and the recognition of the innovation potential of the EPOS infrastructure. All this corroborates the importance of measuring impact through an appropriate and effective approach.

This report presented the methodology to measure the impact of the EPOS IP communication activities. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) adopted for communication activities have been updated since those foreseen at M6 of the project. These KPIs represent only one category of the KPIs adopted to monitor the overall impact of the EPOS IP (see Deliverable D3.3). In reporting the achievements of EPOS communication, this document also describes a first retrospective impact assessment at M23, which will serve to identify the expected outputs at M48 in the forthcoming months.

The results of this first impact assessment of EPOS communication are encouraging and provide helpful indications for further implementing and strengthening the communication work plan. The expected values of the KPIs listed in Table 2 have been assessed by taking into account the key objectives of the EPOS Implementation Phase, the workflow designed in the Description of Action and the timeline followed in the first two years of the project. The impact assessment and analysis strongly depends on these adopted values. The rationale for defining the expected outputs of communication KPIs relies on a retrospective analysis of the implementation roadmap and the achieved outputs. This exercise is useful to plan the realistic assessment of communication activities envisioned at M48. A first forward assessment will be conducted at M36 in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the approach and methodology. The further development of qualitative indicators to better justify the expected KPIs values and to interpret the impact assessment is also envisioned in the forthcoming months.

The KPIs adopted in this report and listed in Table 2 are suitable to measure the outputs, outgrowth and outcomes of specific communication activities performed using specific tools (e.g. website, intranet, social media) and dedicated events targeted to the EPOS objectives. However, it is important to emphasize that communication is also essential in almost all the other activities undertaken to build the EPOS infrastructure. The legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC, for instance, requires the effective engagement of governments (a specific target audience of the EPOS Communication Plan) at the highest possible level of engagement corroborated by the approval of key documents for the EPOS sustainability plan. The same is true for the implementation of the ICT functional architecture as well as for the validation of the EPOS data and service provision. It is extremely difficult to isolate the impact of communication to maximize the impact of these activities. To tackle this challenge, we plan to perform the impact assessment of the EPOS activities through different groups of dedicated KPIs (see a preliminary description in D3.3), and subsequently to adapt specific qualitative indicators to these KPIs that will allow us to interpret the outgrowth and the outcomes of the communication. In other words, we plan to also interpret the results of the impact assessment depicted in Table 2 through an integrated impact analysis of specific activities for different key target audiences.